

DEAN'S LEADERSHIP STYLES AND JOB PERFORMANCE AMONGST NURSING EDUCATORS IN A NURSING COLLEGE IN SUBANG JAYA

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ABSTRACT

Nursing leadership is one of the critical areas that can influence workforce outcomes and the health system. Although leadership is recognized as an important part of nursing service, however, the knowledge of the dean's leadership style among nursing educators in Malaysia is still limited and requires further investigation. The objective of this research was to explore the relationships between the dean's leadership styles and job performance among nursing educators at one of the nursing colleges located in Subang Jaya. The research used a quantitative research method, by employing a four-point Likert scale survey questionnaire, to investigate the relationship between leadership styles and the job performance of nursing educators. This research selected 45 out of 50 nursing educators based on Krejcie and Morgan's sampling table using a convenience sampling technique. The data were analyzed using SPSS software. Descriptive analysis showed that Democratic leadership style was the most favorable leadership style among nurse educators. Overall, the job performance of nursing educators was satisfactory. Correlation analysis indicated a close relationship between democratic leadership and the job performance of nursing educators. The multiple regression analysis further confirmed that democratic leadership style has contributed significantly to nurse educators' job performance. The results from this study provided useful information that might be useful to assist the deans in nursing colleges to deal with leadership issues in order to enhance the job performance of nursing educators.

Keywords: Leadership Styles, Job Performance, Democratic, Authoritarian, Laissez-Faire, Dean, Nursing Educators.

INTRODUCTION

In this era of radical reform, the nursing profession in Malaysia faces several problems as a consequence of fast socio-economic development and also as a result of changes happening inside the country's healthcare system (Barnett et al., 2010). Both of these reasons have had a substantial influence on the growth of nursing education in Malaysia, as seen by the rise in the number of nursing schools from a total of 46 increases to 2008 to 106 in 2010 (Ibrahim, 2008). As a result of this tremendous expansion, the need for adequately certified nurse educators with the requirement of good performance has expanded (Khatijah, 2010). In fact, the nursing leaders must have the ability to inspire, encourage, and energize people

to commit to work diligently toward reaching institutional objectives. All of these must happen at nursing institutions in order to develop high-level qualities among nursing students throughout their studies. Obviously, healthcare organizations are constantly undergoing significant changes, and demanding exceptional leadership from the leaders.

Healthcare institutions cannot grow and prosper unless they have effective nursing educators and leaders. This implies that healthcare institutions must identify the best leadership style to lead nursing educators in the nursing colleges (Hewison & Griffiths, 2004). Deans' leadership styles and nursing educators' performance abilities can play a significant role to achieve consensus opinions and structure the organization's goals, in addition to provide guidance to the group, ensure group satisfaction, and develop cooperation and performance (Sullivan and Decker, 2005). However, Jones (2005) contends that in order to develop leadership characteristics, nurses themselves must also first regard themselves as leaders and possess the ability to lead with great-quality of job performance. These abilities are acquired via a constant process of education, experience, and collaboration with professional mentors.

However, nursing deans are often promoted from inside the academic ranks as faculty members, and most of the time they get little to almost no formal training conducted for their new duties in the academic community (Bray, 2008; Wolverton, Wolverton, & Gmelch, 1999). The majority of the deans learn their job tasks and responsibilities on their own. When it comes to their relationship with faculty members, nursing deans have a unique set of challenges: they are supposed to support, regulate, and share governance with faculty while also being responsible to senior university administrators, as well as internal and external stakeholders (Bright & Richards, 2002). As a result, they commonly faced with stress in their employment since they perceive themselves to be both teachers and administrators and the engagement with the subordinates is not on good terms and the ability to lead the faculty members may be failed due to their rigidity in leadership practices. Since there are still not many researches that have been conducted to identify the relationship between leadership styles and job performance of nursing educators in the nursing colleges in Malaysia context, hence, this study is deemed to be timely to be conducted.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Nyiha (2015) stated that a leadership style is defined as a leader's technique while providing direction, motivating people and implementing plans in the organization to achieve the predetermined goals. Leadership is a process that is able to influence people individually or in communities according to James (2015) and Vroom & Jago (2007). Different leadership leaders may lead their subordinates in different ways. A democratic leader tries to gain total participation in the decision-making process, Authoritarian leaders lead their groups with instructions, and Laissez-faire leaders give the authority to the group without much intervention. On the other hand, job performance can be interpreted as the achievement from employees based on their responsibilities assigned by their leaders. These well-performed employees would usually bring along a positive boost to an institute's productivity. As stated by Meyer & Peng (2005), job performance refers to the outcome that a person has achieved in the organization relating to their attitude, in which the leadership in the organization may recognize as productive or counterproductive. In general, good job performance can be

accomplished when the employees are able to reach the expectation of the leader or employer and are capable of giving success to the organization.

Nurse educators, despite their modest size in Malaysia, play a significant role in shaping the future of the nursing profession because of their commitment to educate and train the next generation of nursing professionals. They instil a sense of dedication and professionalism in others by setting an example and leading by example. In addition to teaching students how to care for patients and lead others, they are supposed to give a sound theoretical foundation on which students may build upon when they begin their careers as nurses (Barrett and Goldenberg, 1988). However, Barrett and Goldenberg (1988) found that teachers of nursing were "fairly happy" with their jobs. In addition, they stated, "inquiring minds want to know: Educators in the nursing field seem to think that a slightly pleased" response is acceptable. Clearly, the answer is no (p. 24)". To create a working environment that encourages productivity and the retention of capable and dedicated nursing educators, it is critical to identify the elements such as types of leadership that might affect their job performance. When it comes to the future of nursing and patient care, it is these people who will have a beneficial influence.

In previous studies, leadership styles are most likely to have some correlation with job performance in an organization. Herbst (2013) investigated the relationship between servant leadership and student accomplishment, concluding that servant leadership behaviours improve teachers' efficacy in the classroom, resulting in higher student achievement. Theoretically, when an employee has failed to perform his job efficiently, several factors leading to such a cause might need to be examined. One of these factors concerned is the leadership style of the leader in that particular organization. It is necessary to assess whether the present organisational leadership is helpful, as well as whether it enhances work characteristics and motivate people to perform their job at their best (Johari & Yahya, 2009).

Northouse (2018) said that removing hurdles and defining routes for educators to accomplish their jobs are important parts of good leadership, and that this is supported by research. In order to be a great leader, leaders must present a set of instructions that contain action plans, for example, when and how to implement a strategy, motivate employees, set challenging goals, maintain amicable relationships, being able to be more flexible and so on. In this case, the dean plays a very important role in promoting the job performance of the nursing educators in a nursing college. According to Hamilton (2016), leaders have a significant influence on the job performance of their staff. On the other hand, Owoeye (1999) elaborated those variables in employment performance included effective teaching, preparation for lessons, efficient use of work arrangements, effective supervision, student monitoring and discipline which are all virtues that teachers should sustain effectively in the school systems. It would be possible to assess the teacher's performance in this regard by examining annual reports of teacher activities in terms of teaching performance, lesson preparation, subject mastery, competence, and commitment to job and extracurricular activities (Ozurouke et al., 2011).

Many studies have been published to support the direct effectiveness of principals' leadership styles on teacher job performance. Imhangbe et al. (2018), for example, analyzed the influence of principal leadership styles on teacher job performance in public senior secondary schools in Edo State, Nigeria discovered that democratic leadership style has a

pretty large influence on teacher job performance. Based on their study, leaders who imply a democratic leadership style can enhance teacher job performance to a higher level. Omeke and Onah (2007) conducted a descriptive design research to explore the effect of principals' leadership styles on secondary school teachers' performance and satisfaction in the Nsukka Education Zone of the state of Enugu also found that democratic leadership styles were mainly shown to improve teachers' job performance and satisfaction.

Some studies like Ozuruoke et al., (2011) found that the more authoritarian a leader is, the more effective his or her subordinate is. Besides, Okoji (2016) investigated the relationship between the leadership style of secondary school administrators and teacher performance in a rural Ondo State, Nigeria also found a significant correlation between authoritarian leadership and teacher performance. However, Akerele (2007) in another study found no relationship between school heads' autocratic leadership style and teachers' job performance at secondary schools in Lagos, Nigeria, but there was a relationship identified between democratic leadership and teacher's job performance, suggesting that administrators who adopt democratic leadership approach can help teachers perform better.

Other than that, there was a study in Nigeria on Laissez-faire leadership and teacher performance (Ejaigu, 2013; Ozuruoke et al., 2012) which found that complete delegation without follow-up mechanisms may result in performance problems, which are likely to have an effect on the job performance of teachers. Obviously, laissez-faire leadership is not the best leadership style to use in the school system because complete delegation without follow-up mechanisms may result in performance problems, which are likely to have an influence on the job performance of teachers. This is in agreement with a study by Ejaigu (2013), where the finding showed that administrators' leadership styles affected business educators' job performance in Delta State, Nigeria.

Undeniably, effective leadership, according to Mahdinezhad et al., (2013), is critical to an organization's improved performance and growth. Leadership is considered as a function and an important component of management. According to Shafie et al., (2013), leaders need to choose the correct leadership style to establish human relationships, thus maximizing the human capabilities in their organization. Effective leadership styles, according to McGrath & MacMillan (2000), can help improve performance when new obstacles arise. In a nursing institution, the dean's leadership has a variety of responsibilities to be performed. Some of these responsibilities of leadership include ensuring high performance and an optimal work environment, formulating strategies and aligning with the institution's goals, fostering collaboration among members, ensuring compliance with rules and compliance of professional standards with operating procedures, and problem-solving and decision-making. All of this demand a flexible leadership style that is not too rigid while running any nursing faculty or institution even though democratic leadership may deem to be the most appropriate leadership style under the most common circumstances.

METHODOLOGY

RESEARCH DESIGN

This study employed a quantitative method of descriptive-correlational research design. The rationale for selecting this research design was to investigate the relationship between variables of dean's leadership styles and the job performance of nursing educators. This research design will help to determine the direction and strength of the relationship between the two variables investigated in this study. According to Lowhorn, (2007), quantitative research is better than qualitative research at establishing causality because of the precise measurements and controlled environment. Creswell (2005) claimed correlational research is suitable to explore relationships between the independent and dependent variables. Hence, in order to figure out the influences of the dean's leadership styles on the job performance of nursing educators, this research design was deemed appropriate. Furthermore, Gall et al. (2007) have agreed that correlational research designs should be used in analyses that help to determine the relationship between the research variables or reveal a causal-comparative relationship.

POPULATION AND SAMPLING

The study's target population was nursing educators at one of the nursing colleges in Subang Jaya, who were actively engaged with the teaching and supervision of the nursing students. According to Wellman and Kruger (2003), the term "target population" refers to a group of people who are likely to participate in a research project. Based on the sampling table of Krejcie and Morgan (1970), a total of 50 nursing educators were chosen from one of the nursing colleges in Subang Jaya and finally, a total of 45 individuals have answered the survey questionnaires that were sent through WhatsApp and online Telegram.

The questionnaires were distributed to the nursing educators using the convenience sampling method. Additionally, the term refers to participants in population studies who are readily accessible to the researcher [S. K. & Lisa Given, 2008]. As defined by Dörnyei (2007), convenience sampling refers to those who work as clinical instructors in the nursing college and have at least one year of experience are eligible to be included in the study. Particularly, these participants are nursing educators who are actively engaged in teaching and supervising the nursing students in the nursing college.

The questionnaires were distributed to 45 nursing educators through a Google Form, with clear instructions stated on how to complete the survey questionnaire for each respondent to follow. Due to the Covid-19 pandemic and the Movement Control Order (MCO), the application of Google form has emerged as the most effective method to collect the survey data. The questionnaires were sent to respondents using online channels such as the WhatsApp and Telegram applications. All the respondents were given enough time to complete the questionnaire before it was turned in.

INSTRUMENTATION

A set of questionnaires on leadership styles was adopted from Northouse (2009) and the items on teacher job performance were adapted from Atsebeha (2016). This questionnaire was converted into an online Google form questionnaire and distributed to 45 nursing

educators through WhatsApp and Telegram applications. To meet the purpose of this study, the questionnaire was divided into three sections. The first part of the questionnaire in section A was related to respondents' *Demographic Information*. It deals with gender, age, race, number of years in the service and number of years in the nursing college. Section B adopted the Leadership Styles Instrument from Northouse (2009). This instrument was categorised into three dimensions and contained a total of 18 items of *Authoritarian Leadership* (7 items), *Democratic Leadership* (6 items) and *Laissez-faire Leadership* (5 items). The second instrument in section C was adapted from the *Job Performance Questionnaire (JPQ)* from Atsebeha (2016) consisting of 22 questions with five dimensions. This instrument was chosen for its characteristic that was aligned with the focus of this research. The original component of the instrument contained a total of 22 items: teaching planning (5 items), classroom organization (4 items), monitoring and evaluation (4 items), classroom atmosphere and discipline (4 items) and nursing educators' leadership (5 items). As an adaptation of the instrument, some terms were slightly changed from 'workbooks' to 'assignments' or 'project assignment', 'teachers' to 'nursing educators' and 'school' to 'institution' and 'the workbooks of learners are regularly marked' to 'the assignments of learners are regularly marked', with the rest remaining the same. Items 11 and 15 had amendments to some extent, such as "The workbooks of learners are regularly signed by both teachers and parents" to "The assignment projects of learners are regularly monitored and guided" and "Classrooms are clean and appropriately decorated" to "Classrooms are clean and in a conducive and serene atmosphere".

Since Likert (1932) established the summative rating scale, also known as the Likert-type scale, hence, the researchers have sought the number of scale points (item answer alternatives) that optimize dependability. In this study, the four-point Likert Scale was used. The scales range from 1 to 4, there is no middle category or neutral scale to avoid the central tendency problem in statistical analysis (Nemoto & Beglar, 2014). Thus, in this study, the respondents need to evaluate the set of questionnaires for all sections by using a 4-point Likert Scale (1 = strongly disagree, 2 = disagree, 3 = agree, and 4 = strongly agree).

DATA ANALYSIS

All of the data were analysed using IBM SPSS software, and all numerical data was collected, categorised, tabulated, and summarised to derive some kind of meaning in accordance with the research objectives. Descriptive analysis was deployed to answer research question 1 (RQ1) and 2 (RQ2). Meanwhile, an inferential type of correlational analysis was used to answer research question 3 (RQ3) to measure the statistical relationship between the two research variables. Finally, an inferential type of multiple regression analysis was used to answer research question 4 (RQ4) to identify the contribution of the dimensions of the independent variables of leadership styles towards the variance of the dependent variable of the job performance of nursing educators.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Demographic Analysis

This section presents the findings of the demographic data of the respondents. It reports the respondents' background information such as their gender, age, ethnicity, years of service (experience) and years of service in the nursing college. A total of 45 respondents participated in the survey resulting from various backgrounds from each of them.

Table 1. Demographic Analysis

Variables		Frequency	Percent
Gender of Nursing Educators	Male	1	2.2
	Female	44	97.8
Ages of Nursing Educators	20 to 30 years old	8	17.8
	31 to 40 years old	20	44.4
	Above 40 years old	17	37.8
Ethnicity of Nursing Educators	Malay	29	64.4
	Chinese	3	6.7
	Indian	13	28.9
Duration of Service as Nursing Educators	Less than 2 years	5	11.1
	2 to 5 years	8	17.8
	6 to 10 years	11	24.4
	More than 10 years	21	46.7
Number of Years in The Current Institute	Less than 2 years	7	15.6
	2 to 5 years	21	46.7
	6 to 10 years	12	26.7
	More than 10 years	5	11.1

The demographic characteristics of this study were measured by gender, age, ethnicity, duration of service and number of years in the current Institute. The total number of male respondents involved with this research is 2.2% (N=1) which was much lower than the female which was 97.8% (N=44) respondents for gender. The age of respondents was grouped into 20 to 30, 31 to 40 and above 40 years old. From the total respondents, most of the educators' ages were ranged from 31 to 40 years old which contributed to 44.4% (N=20). A total of 17.8% of the respondents' age was from 20 to 30 years (N=8), and 37.8% of them were above 40 years old (N=17). The ethnicity of the nursing educators was grouped into three categories of ethnicity namely: Malay, Chinese and Indian. Out of this total, 64.4% of them are Malay (N=29), 3% are Chinese (N=3), and 13% are Indian (N=13). Educators' duration of service was divided into four categories namely: less than 2 years, 2 to 5 years, 6 to 10 years and more than 10 years. From the total respondents, most of the educators 46.7% (N=21) have been working for more than 10 years. A total of 24.4% (N=11) respondents have 6 to 10 years of duration of service while 17.8% (N=8) respondents have 2 to 5 years of service duration. However, only 11.1% (N=5) of the respondents have less than 2 years of duration of service. The number of years nursing educators have been working in the current institute was grouped into; Less than 2 years, 2 to 5 years, 6 to 10 years and more than 10 years. From the total respondents, most of the educators (N=21) with 46.7% have 2 to 5 years duration of service in this nursing college and (N=12) with 26.7% respondents have 6 to 10 years of service. Meanwhile (N=7) with 15.6% have less than 2 years and only (N=5) with 11.1% respondents have more than 10 years duration of service in this nursing college.

Research Question 1:

What is the mean score of the dean's leadership styles amongst nursing educators in a nursing college in Subang Jaya, in terms of Authoritarian Leadership Style, Democratic Leadership Style and Laissez- Faire Leadership Style?

Table 2. Mean Score of Dean's Leadership Styles Perceived by Nursing Educators

Leadership Styles	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Democratic	45	3.11	.23
Authoritarian	45	2.70	.40
Laissez Faire	45	2.60	.45
Overall Mean Score	45	2.80	.25

Scale: 1= Strongly disagree; 2= Disagree; 3= Agree; 4= Strongly agree

Based on Table 2, the mean score of the dean's leadership styles shows that the Democratic leadership style depicts the highest mean, as compared to other leadership styles, at 3.11 (SD=0.23). This indicates that the Democratic leadership style was the highly rated leadership style perceived by the educators at a nursing college in Subang Jaya. From the statistics, it has been identified that the Authoritarian leadership style was rated as the second most perceived leadership style with a mean score of 2.70 (SD=0.40), and lastly by the Laissez-faire leadership style with a mean score of 2.60 (SD=0.45). This means that the Laissez-faire leadership style was the least favorable dean's leadership style rated by the nursing educators at this college.

Research Question 2:

What is the mean score of job performance amongst nursing educators in a nursing college in Subang Jaya, in terms of teaching planning, classroom organization, monitoring and evaluation, classroom atmosphere and discipline, and nursing educators' leadership?

Table 3. Mean Score of Job Performance Amongst Nursing Educators

Job Performance	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Nursing Educators Leadership	45	3.05	.22
Teaching Planning	45	3.05	.20
Classroom Organization	45	3.03	.21
Classroom Atmosphere and Discipline	45	2.89	.30
Monitoring and Evaluation	45	2.47	.73
Overall Mean Score	45	3.18	.20

Scale: 1= Strongly disagree; 2= Disagree; 3= Agree; 4= Strongly agree

Table 3 depicts the overall mean score of job performance among educators at a nursing college in Subang Jaya which is 3.18 (SD=0.20). Nursing Educators' Leadership showed the highest mean score of 3.05 (SD=0.22), while Teaching Planning also shared an equal mean score of 3.05 (SD=0.120). This indicates that nursing educators at a nursing college in Subang Jaya do have good nursing leadership and teaching planning that will contribute to their job performance. The item of Classroom Organization shows the third most perceived job performance that resulted in a mean score of 3.03 (SD=0.21) followed by Classroom Atmosphere and Discipline which achieved a mean score of 2.89 (SD = 0.30) and the least aspect of the job performance of Monitoring and Evaluation falls into the mean score is 2.47 (SD=0.73).

Research Question 3

Is there any significant relationship between the dean's leadership styles and job performance amongst nursing educators in a nursing college in Subang Jaya?

H₀: There is no significant relationship between the dean's leadership styles and job performance amongst nursing educators in a nursing college in Subang Jaya.

H₁: There is a significant relationship between the dean's leadership styles and job performance amongst nursing educators in a nursing college in Subang Jaya.

Table 4. Relationship Between Dean's Leadership Styles and Job Performance Amongst Nursing Educators

	Leadership Styles	Job Performance
Democratic	Pearson Correlation	.775**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
	N	45
Laissez Faire	Pearson Correlation	.361*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.015
	N	45
Authoritarian	Pearson Correlation	.126
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.410
	N	45

Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).*

Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).**

The Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to analyze the relationship between the dean's leadership styles (independent variable) and job performance (dependent variable). The finding from Table 4 inferred that there was a positive and significant relationship between the Democratic leadership style and job performance ($r = .775$, $p < .001$). However, it was indicated that the Laissez-faire leadership style dimension and job

performance ($r = .361$, $p < .05$) did have a positive, moderate and significant relationship. Thus, we rejected the null hypotheses for both democratic and laissez-faire leadership styles.

Research Question 4

What is the relative contribution of the dean's leadership style towards the dependent variable of job performance amongst nursing educators in a nursing college in Subang Jaya?

Based on the correlation above, a multiple linear regression was used to test if the Democratic dean's leadership style and Laissez-faire dean's leadership style have significantly predicted job performance.

Table 5. Multiple Regression Analysis of Leadership styles towards Job Performance Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.964	.264		3.653	.001
	Democratic	.648	.086	.731	7.499	.000
	Laissez Faire	.076	.043	.171	1.757	.086

R Square = .628, Adjusted R Square = .610, F = 35.47, P < .01

a. Dependent Variable: Job Performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), Laissez Faire, Democratic Dean's Leadership Style

Table 5 shows the model summary, which identifies that $R = .793$ which is a square root of R -Square = 0.628 and it is the correlation between the observed and predicted values of the nursing educators' job performance (dependent variable). R square is also called the coefficient determination. R square is the proportion of variance in the Job Performance (dependent variable) which can be predicted from the dean's leadership style (independent variable). This value indicates that 62.8% of the variance in lectures' job performance can be predicted by democratic and Laissez Faire leadership style.

The coefficient for the democratic leadership style was 0.73. Hence, for every unit increase in the democratic dean's leadership style, we expected a .73-point increase in the nursing educators' job performance. This was statistically significant at $t = 7.5$, $p < 0.001$. However, the table inferred that Laissez-faire was not a significant predictor to job performance at $t = 1.76$, $p > 0.05$. The overall regression was statistically significant ($R^2 = .628$, $F(2, 42) = 35.47$, $p < 0.01$). Thus, only democratic leadership style can be used to reliably predict nursing educators' job performance.

DISCUSSION

DEAN'S LEADERSHIP STYLES PERCEIVED BY NURSING EDUCATORS

The highest mean score revealed the data was interpreted on democratic leadership style dimensions ($M= 3.11$, $SD= .23$), portrayed that the respondents rated high on the Democratic leadership style. Northouse (2007) mentioned that leadership is a person's ability to manage a group of individuals to accomplish the mutual goals. Verba (2015) supported that good leadership promotes innovation, teamwork, and creativity, and individuals are frequently involved in projects that result in improved performance, job satisfaction, and productivity. This indicates that in this study, leaders will demonstrate and support the use of democratic leadership as a strategy for influencing nursing educators' performance. As a result, nursing educators' who followed these leadership approaches were more likely to be more productive which means to perform better on the job. Leaders should not depend on their legal power to force people to do what they're instructed; instead, they should have an initiative in connecting with their subordinates, as well as extending their subordinates' interests (Northouse, 2007). Griffith's (2005) discovered that democratic leadership abilities are related to higher levels of teacher happiness which is significant in many ways because democratic school leadership decreases teacher isolation, delegates power to others, and actively promotes the school norm.

The Authoritarian leadership style was rated with the mean score ($M= 2.70$, $SD= .40$) which showed that the Authoritarian leadership style was less favoured by nursing educators. Research findings from Boehm, et al., (2015) stated that Authoritarian leadership refers to those leaders who make decisions without consulting or obtaining the approval of their team members. According to Adair (2002), under authoritarian leadership, only one person has the total power and influence over his or her employees. The decision made by the authoritarian leaders was regarded as the golden law, never to be questioned or disrupted. In certain situations, this type of leadership will help the subordinate to maintain their performance. Those who follow them are obligated to work or to abide by the restrictions established at each milestone. In other words, the autocratic leader is in command and believes he has the authority to treat his subordinates in any way he pleases. According to Dawson (2002), the autocratic approach may provide impressive outcomes in a very short amount of time. In the long run, however, excessive use of authority will have a negative influence on productivity. People either quit because they are bored and dissatisfied, or they become lonely and depressed of tedious, repetitive work that lacks both originality and innovation, and hence lose interest and motivation to do anything.

Meanwhile, the lowest means score between the three dimensions was reported on Laissez-faire leadership style ($M = 2.60$, $SD = .45$). The finding indicates the least preferred leadership style by the nursing educators. This research was consistent with the findings made by previous researchers (Bass & Riggio, 2006) which described this type of leadership as characterized by leaders and subordinates having no way to communicate and guide one another. Leaders that avoid taking responsibility, do not attend to the needs of their followers, do not provide feedback, and put off making decisions are bad examples of leadership. Richard et al. (2009) stated that Laissez-faire is a leadership style in which responsibility and power are delegated to workers; the leaders give little or no guidance to employees. Previous researchers stated that this type of leadership is occasionally seen as ineffective leadership (Aydin et al., 2013; Bass, 1990; Lam & O'Higgins, 2012).

JOB PERFORMANCE OF NURSING EDUCATORS

The finding revealed the mean score of job performance amongst nursing educators in one of the nursing colleges in Subang Jaya. The findings indicated that the highest mean score was interpreted on nursing educator leadership and teaching planning, and then followed by classroom organization, classroom atmosphere and discipline, and lastly monitoring and evaluation. According to Hart (1955), "teacher leadership" is the act of influencing others' beliefs, behaviours, and values. Students appreciate compassionate teachers who foster a sense of community and family in the classroom and make learning fun (Howard, 2001). Thus, the students feel at ease and know that their nursing educators care about them when nursing educators demonstrate understanding which later will create a positive learning environment for them. It is necessary to determine whether the current organisational structure is helpful or not, as well as to refine work characteristics to encourage individuals to achieve their maximum potential (Johari & Yahya, 2009). According to Leithwood et al. (2004), their study on "How Leadership Influences Student Learning" is organised around three themes: setting direction, fostering talent, and constructing an environment. Effective teachers are influenced by both face-to-face contact and the structure of the work environment created by strong leadership (Ogawa & Bossert, 1995). Hence, a great performance by the employees can be produced once the great leader opposes a good support system.

Meanwhile, the lowest mean score between the five dimensions reported on monitoring and evaluation was contradicted by the findings from Andrews and Soder (1987) who emphasized that higher-performing education put a greater emphasis on ensuring that professionals monitor and evaluate student growth regularly. In addition, Bamberg (1991) proposed that an engagement of educators in classroom assessment and subsequent feedback was also associated with higher-achieving education. Educators at this kind of learning institution reported that their management established clear standards for educators' performance and conducted regular classroom inspections to assist them in improving their teaching and at the same time keep monitoring the students' progress carefully. These elements will drive the teaching and learning process in the classroom whether the teachers are happy or not to provide a good teaching session with the students.

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN OF DEAN'S LEADERSHIP STYLES AND JOB PERFORMANCE AMONGST NURSING EDUCATORS IN A NURSING COLLEGES IN SUBANG JAYA

There was a positive, strong and very significant relationship between the dean's leadership styles and job performance identified in the correlation analysis. This finding is aligned with many empirical studies that proved that there was a relationship between leadership styles and job performance. In a study conducted by Mehrab et al. (2014), they observed a correlation between administrators' leadership style and teacher performance. The findings of Okoji (2016), also identified a significant relationship between leadership style and teachers' job performance. Al-Maliki et.al, (2018) claimed that leaders have a beneficial effect on the organization's efficiency by influencing team members' work performance. In other words, leadership styles most likely correlate with the productivity of the job performance in the organization. This means that leaders must set a wise goal or effectively manage their leadership styles to ensure that the organization meets its objectives through good subordinate performance. This study was also supported by a previous study by Doris Masal and Rick Vogel (2016). They identified the important role of leadership in performance management and explained how leadership styles can correlate with job performance. Several (statistically significant) positive correlations between leadership style and job

performance have also been observed by Hawkins and Dulewicz (2009). Thus, the finding on leadership styles correlate to job performance is acceptable, however, only certain leadership styles might be relevant to give the improvement on educators' performance.

THE RELATIVE CONTRIBUTION OF LEADERSHIP STYLES TOWARDS JOB PERFORMANCE OF NURSING EDUCATORS

The multiple regression indicates that 62.8% of the variance of nursing educators' job performance can be predicted by the Democratic leadership style. The multiple linear regression further revealed that the coefficient for Democratic leadership style was .731 with a significant value at $t=7.5, p<0.001$. The result can be interpreted that for every unit increase in Democratic leadership style, we can expect a .731-point increase in the nursing educators' job performance.

Research from Siskin (1994) and Gronn (2000) reported that there were significant relationships between democratic and teachers' job performance which means that the deans who use the Democratic leadership style can boost the job performance among nursing educators. Democratic style of leadership which is known as the participative style will be able to encourage the subordinates to be part of the decision-making process. Previously, several researchers have revealed that democratic is more effective than autocratic (Dolly and Nonyelum, 2018). According to Mba (2004), strong levels of employee enthusiasm are always fostered under democratic leadership styles. Ajibade (2010) said that the democratic leadership style is the most often employed leadership style when the results of his study show that democratic leadership style has the greatest effect on employees' job performance, followed by Autocratic and Laissez-faire leadership. The employees are allowed to participate in decision-making by offering their thoughts, comments, and recommendations due to the democratic leadership style.

According to results by Iyayi (2000) and Ezeuwa (2005), Democratic leaders consider their subordinates as collaborators and partners in advancement with objective suggestions for addressing organisational challenges. The findings of this study are also consistent with those of other researchers, such as Haruni and Mafwimbo (2014), who discovered that school principals in elementary schools tended to embrace democratic leadership styles as a general principle. We can gain a lot of knowledge about our systems from the democratic leadership style that is prevalent in low-performing elementary schools especially to enhance job satisfaction and will affect the job performance of employees, according to the researchers. However, Nwaigwe (2015) found the finding through his study on the Influence of Head Librarians' Leadership Styles on the Job Satisfaction of Librarians in tertiary institution libraries in Imo State, Nigeria that although head library professionals tend to use democratic leadership styles, however, autocratic and laissez-faire leadership styles did have an influence on subordinates' job satisfaction and job performances as well. Obviously, most empirical studies support that democratic leadership styles can enhance the job performance in any organization. However, the leadership styles should be able to apply accordingly to the condition and situation so that it would give positive feedback towards the subordinates especially.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The finding of this study shows that the democratic leadership style gave an effluent to the job performance as perceived by nursing educators in a nursing college in Subang Jaya. Research has shown that effective leadership improves the overall efficiency of higher education institutions; as a result, academic leaders must employ appropriate leadership styles that refine the skills and abilities of academic leaders and assist others in achieving better job performance (Mahdinezhad, Suandi, Silong, Daud, & Omar, 2013). Furthermore, it is said that leadership styles may contribute to the development of both leaders' leadership competencies as well as their subordinates' job performance and commitment. The following recommendations were made based on the findings of the study;

1. First and foremost, the nursing college's upper management should encourage the deans to use democratic leadership style practices while carrying out their administrative duties. This advice may be accomplished by giving deans or heads of nursing academics proper training on the qualities and significance of the Democratic leadership style, as well as on how to strengthen their own leadership capabilities, and skills while not being too rigid with one leadership style.
2. Training courses for the dean and nursing educators should be incorporated into nursing educators' training programmes in such a manner that deans of nursing colleges may learn about the Democratic leadership style and how to apply it successfully use in their institutions.
3. Nursing educators must have a clear understanding of their role and job scope and have the skills, knowledge, experience, and competencies to work effectively and efficiently in an academic setting. Both the leader and the subordinate must possess a strong relationship so that there is trust and respect and they must seek to know more and be willing to share their knowledge, education, experience, and skills so that others in the environment can benefit. The existence of a strong professional relationship between the dean and nursing educators' relationship must be ensured. Leaders can use the findings from this study as a reference point to build working relationships in the organization that fosters a higher-performing organization.
4. The practice of a Laissez-faire leadership style should be implemented with caution to minimize the possible effect on the nursing educators' job performance. The deans or head academics of the nursing faculty should be encouraged to lead their subordinates to use authoritarian methods or suitable leadership styles, especially where the subordinates are having problems or lacking in providing the classroom atmosphere and discipline.
5. Give nursing educators the support they need and allocate resources appropriately to demonstrate leadership and willingness to make them able to create a better classroom atmosphere and more discipline.
6. In addition, the organisation needs to ensure that there is respect for the uniqueness and contributions of others, regardless of their role and position, status, age, gender, years of practice, and so on. It is the goal of education to create a safer and better working environment for staff to enhance the good relationship between leaders and staff. Fostering respect from leaders and nursing educators will ensure a trusting relationship and a willingness on both sides to work collaboratively together.

7. Nursing college's management should put policies in place that discourage the Authoritarian leadership style since it does not show any contribution to enhance employees' performance and growth.
8. Lastly, this current study will contribute to the development of the body of knowledge on nursing in the country. However, various future studies might help to develop effective leadership styles in nursing education and a broader study may be required to verify the results of this study. It is also necessary to have an equal representation of male and female participants in the sample, and data collecting over a longer period might be beneficial since participants will have more time to gather their ideas in answer to the interview questions. The researcher recommends that a bigger sample size need to be used for future research, as well as a more varied sample, to confirm the results and conduct statistical comparisons across studies. It is possible to collect a diversified nursing educator population by employing a database of nursing educators actively working in nursing faculty from all colleges and universities in Malaysia and adopting a mixed methods design research to acquire additional participants and data may also be a successful strategy.

In summary, applying different qualitative data analysis software and tools to interpret the data in this research may provide different or comparable results on leadership styles and job performance, which might be used to effect change and improve the performance of nursing educators. Overall, the findings may be useful in driving change in the nursing education system, particularly in steering nursing educators' performance and organisational performance, and in developing a change in organisational culture to one that supports a democratic style of leadership among leaders, with a central focus on the personal, professional, and educational growth and development of nursing educators.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest regarding this manuscript.

CONTRIBUTION OF AUTHOR

All authors are participants in the data collection, analysis, writing and revising the manuscript.

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